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Synthesis of nanocellulose from sawdust

Savita Sihag, Sheetal*

Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science and Technology, Hisar, 125001, India

*Corresponding author: Sheetal (dahiyasheetal619@gmail.com)

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Introduction: Sawdust is basically considered as a timber-industrial waste that pollutes the environment can become a valuable commodity which is considered in three ways: Manufacturing, Energy and Agricultural utilization. Nanocellulose is derived from cell wall of plants and animals. The cellulosic biomass is mainly constituted by cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. Lignin has 10 to 25 percent, hemicellulose has 20 to 35 percent and cellulose in highest quantity i.e., 35 to 50 percent by weight of dried biomass (1). These are divided into two categories- Nanoobject cellulose and Nanostructured cellulose. Nanoobject cellulose has size of 10 to 100 μm and latter has size of 1 to 50 nm. Cellulose microcrystal and microfibril fall under nanoobject cellulose and cellulose nanocrystal and nanofibril falls under cellulose nanostructure (2).

Methods: In this study, the raw material used was sawdust made from *Tectona Grandis*, known as Indian Hardwood 'Sangwan'. It was collected from a carpenter shop in Hisar. The sawdust was washed thoroughly by tap water to dislodge all the foreign elements attached with sawdust, grinded and sieved for further use in nanocellulose synthesis. First of all, alkali treatment is given using 5% NaOH, then bleaching treatment is given using 8% sodium chlorite, then acid hydrolysis is done using 20% sulphuric acid after that ultrasonication and at last cryo-crushing is done to obtain nanocellulose.

Results & Discussions:

Fig. 1. Synthesis of nanocellulose (untreated sawdust, alkali treated, bleached fibres, acid hydrolysis, nanocellulose)

Nanocellulose is synthesised by giving various treatments to untreated sawdust such as alkali treatment, bleaching process, acid hydrolysis and obtained the synthesised nanocellulose.

Conclusions: Nanocellulose is successfully synthesised using sawdust.

Keywords: Nanocellulose, Sawdust, Acid hydrolysis, Ultrasonication

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